

Is there a Latin American model of diamond publishing? Exploring the University Portals

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Abstract

Numerous initiatives and academic organizations have highlighted awareness on the marketization of scholarly publishing and the need to strengthen its future through diamondisation. Latin America is often presented as a model in this regard. However, the diversity of the region's publishing landscape and the coexistence of different editorial models remain insufficiently examined. It is well known that this resilient ecosystem relies on non-commercial platforms and indexing systems such as Redalyc, Latindex, Biblat and SciELO, as well as on the widespread use of Open Journal Systems (OJS). Less emphasized is the central role played by universities, which possess the experience and capacity to sustain community-led publishing initiatives. This paper first presents a global cartography of indexed diamond journals updated to June 2025, based on an aggregated dataset of multiple sources comprising 17,855 journals, highlighting Latin America's contribution to quality diamond publishing. It then examines the results of a regional survey of University Portals conducted between August and October 2025, covering 741 portals responsible for 10,823 active journals. Finally, it is argued that supporting these institutional organizations offers a realistic pathway to advance diamond scholarly publishing, while acknowledging that each region shall find suitable routes according with the features of their academic journals.

Keywords

Diamond publishing; University portals; Open Access; Latin America; non-commercial platforms

Introduction

Open Access was conceived as a path to democratize the circulation of knowledge and expand the audiences for scholarly communication along with the emergence of internet and digitalization. However, during this transformation, the transition to open access grew rapidly as a commercial business model and the "golden route" as defined by the pioneers of the movement ceased to be "free, open access, and immediate". It evolved, eventually, into a new paywall to increase geometrically the profit rates of the publishing industry (Guédon, 2021; Chan, 2022; Pinfield, 2025). This marketization has severe consequences in terms of money, time, trust and loss

of control by the academic community (Beigel, Crosetto et al 2025). Academic autonomy is at stake in front of aggressive intrusions of the commercial publishers, which points out to the need to align the future of open access publishing towards a re-communalization of the journals (Beigel, 2025b).

In parallel, the hybrid model has featured a particular open access path for a relevant portion of the “high impact” journals included in the WoS and Scopus that evolved as a specific publishing segment in terms of symbolic recognition and commercial revenues. This double publishing track type of journals reinforced two phenomena in scholarly publishing that are being observed with increasing interest in bibliometric studies. First, the transparency issues that surround the APC prices in the journals managed by the big commercial publishers. Second, the backwardness in terms of the open access that is fostered by the closed facet of the hybrid journals, given the fact that the researchers who cannot pay APC are choosing this option.

It was then that the "diamond" label emerged, as a reaction against the growing commodification of open access and its associated asymmetries. But the concrete paths to achieving this are not yet visible. Steinhart et al. (2024) note that what is now called "diamond" open access refers to something that has existed for a long time, as completely free journals, available online, have existed since mid-1990s. It is also pertinent to note that the concept of “diamond” is under scrutiny, given that this mineral embodies the very nature of colonial extraction (Chan, 2023) and it is indeed a good reason to discuss its very definition or even abandon its use.

In recent years, the Coalition S has recognized the inequities and distortions that emerged in scientific communication with the expansion of open access (Mounier & Rooryck, 2023). Diverse initiatives have begun to support global actions in favor of diamond access. Events such as the Diamond Summit in Mexico (2023), in Cape Town (2024) and the reports by OPERAS and Science Europe, provided an initial overview of the global landscape of Diamond journals. It was estimated that there are around 29,000 journals worldwide that do not charge for reading or publishing (Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer et al 2021). But empirical information on these journals is limited to half of them, mainly extracted from one source: DOAJ.

Despite the numerous reports and research projects that attempt to describe the existing “Diamond” journals, there remains a significant gap concerning the global landscape of these journals, what kind of audiences they reach, the indexation services they have, the type of editorial management used and the institutional publishers that support them. The available studies at journal level point out these limitations, while there are several efforts to overcome this gap by observing national publishing landscapes, the university journals and the Latin American regional circuit (Taubert, Sterzik & Bruns 2024; Beigel 2025a; Nazarovets, Taskin & Laakso 2025; Kulczycki et al 2025).

Differently from the marketization that occurred to the journals led by learned societies, the university journals appear with a major autonomy and potential framework for sustainability. Recent surveys have been conducted with different data sources, such as ISSN or national aggregators. Nazarovets, Laakso & Taşkın (2025) recently listed more than 19,000 active titles directly edited by universities or by learned societies in association with universities. This shows that universities have both the experience and the capacity to develop efficient platforms for scholarly communication. They possess experts that can cultivate community-led venues and uphold the ethical integrity of these journals (Nazarovets, 2025).

In this paper, we describe a cartography of indexed diamond journals updated to June 2025, based on an aggregated dataset with multiple data sources, including a total 17,855 journals analyzed by countries. Secondly, we delve into the results of a regional survey of University Portals performed during August-October 2025, examining a total of 741 Portals responsible for the publication of 10,823 active journals. We address the University Portals as a management system, frequently organized by centralized editorial teams working at the Library or the Digital institutional Repository, rarely connected with the University Press -traditionally dedicated to book publishing. Finally, we argue that to support these institutional organizations represents a realistic path to push diamond scholarly publishing. Although there is no one-size-fits-all solution and each region shall assess their pros and cons to find a suitable path to move forward.

The hybrid route and the marketization of community-led publishing

The idea of community-led publishing is a polyphonic one that gained momentum in the last years along with the growth of mega-journals, marketization and predatory journals. One of the possible definitions in use is the idea of the “open access community” which generally scientific agencies, funders, universities, service providers, publishing platforms, open access publishers, among others. COAlition fostered this definition of the open access community, while in other latitudes, the open access ecosystem is made of academic institutions, indexing systems and publishing platforms operating in the public sphere, without the interference of commercial publishers, such as it is the case of Latin America. In its most recent report cOAlition S concludes that Plan S has "galvanized the Open Access community" by raising Open Access profile, drawing publishers to negotiations, harmonizing funder policies, and inspiring initiatives like institutional rights retention and momentum for Diamond OA.

What Plan S “got right” according with the cOAlition S report is in identifying the right levers to pull, primarily by operating as a consortium and engaging with publishers,

while maintaining a flexible approach through various strategies for achieving Open Access (OA). Among the “got wrong” side, it mentions the tenuous link to national-level contexts and its failure to secure support from additional funders, especially from Asia and Latin America/Caribbean, which impacts the credibility of its equitable publishing discourse (COAlition S, 2024). In sum, this open access community, built by the Plan S seems to have facilitated the detachment of scholarly publishing from their national and institutional academic anchorages. The study also stresses that Hybrid Open Access notably increased among cOAlition S funders (COAlition S, 2024). This route has been documented as instrumental for the outrageous increase in APC prices (Haustein, 2024) and a path for a consisting backwardness in open access because of the non-OA choice made by researchers incapable to afford these charges (Beigel, Torres Arroyave & Vélez Cuartas, 2025). Figure 1 shows the rapid increase of the hybrid titles in one source, in only 2 years (2019-2021).

Figure 1 and Table 1

Evolution of hybrid journals 2014-2023

Source: <https://pkm-nrw-e5edb7.pages.ub.uni-bielefeld.de/uni.html>

Jahn (2025) built a multi-source database to examine the impact of transformative agreements on hybrid open access publishing. Analyzing over 13,000 hybrid journals between 2019 and 2023, this research found substantial growth in open access, although most articles remain paywalled. The analysis highlights the dominance of the three largest publishers, Elsevier, Springer Nature, and Wiley, which collectively accounted for 47% of the hybrid journals and 62% of the articles published during

this 5-year period. The results were consistent across all three data sources, showing strong correlations in country-level metrics despite differences in journal coverage and metadata availability. By 2023, transformative agreements enabled the open access option in hybrid journals, with particularly high adoption in European countries. Meanwhile, the number of open Access articles published by researchers in the Global South is frankly low (Frank, Foster & Pagliari 2023; Huais et al., 2026).

Does this mean that the Global South is not part of the open access community? Quite the contrary, this movement finds in a region like Latin America very strong and foundational pillars. It is well known that this publishing ecosystem is fed by public platforms and indexing systems like Redalyc, Latindex, Biblat and Scielo, boosted by using the open code journal system OJS. As a result, there are thousands of diamond journals featured by multilingualism and disciplinary diversity (Beigel, Packer et al 2022; Beigel, Sánchez, Alonso Gamboa et al 2024). What is less highlighted is that these active journals (some of which date back to 1909) are sustained by universities that have both experience and the capacity to develop community-led publishing.

Overall, this Latin American publishing infrastructure can be considered as a regional circuit with different degrees of visibility and impact. Whichever scale and audience they reach, these journals are undoubtedly managed by research groups or faculty members aiming to communicate with a specialized community. An endogenous value system is observed throughout curated journal collections focused on academic quality and autonomous editorship (Beigel 2025c). The university anchorage of most of these venues seems to be the fundamental prevention against predatory publishing and marketization, as the Latindex committee dedicated to detecting spurious journals seem to prove (Latindex 2022).

Mapping indexed diamond journals at a global scale

Building a cartography of indexed diamond journals can be relevant to inform researchers and foster a change in the publishing choices. Several landscape studies have been carried out in recent years, including the Open Access Diamond Journal Study, with empirical results and recommendations. According to this report, the number of diamond journals can be estimated at 29,000, but only half of them is registered in DOAJ. Since 2018, they observe a dwindling tendency of the share of diamond journal articles which coincides with the increase in articles in APC-based journals. They argue that OA diamond sector is diverse in terms of disciplines (60% SSH, 22% science, 17% medicine) and the share by regions also differs: 45% in Europe, 25% in Latin America, 16% in Asia, 5% in the US/Canada (Bosman, Frantsvåg, Kramer et al 2021).

This photography is highly dynamical, as the authors of the report rightly affirm, because mapping diamond journals globally is not an easy task. Beyond the changes produced by journals that are closed while many new are opened, the most contested issue is the data sources available. As we will see further, Latin America's share is underreported because the main source is DOAJ, which covers only part of the journals published in this regional circuit. Our mapping includes only titles indexed in services that can guarantee an evaluation of the academic quality of the publication and not only its integration in a non-curated list of journals, because our final goal is to foster a shift in academic culture. Diamond journals that can certify quality can be rewarded by institutions and funding agencies that embark into a meaningful path towards responsible research assessment. Although it is relevant to note that this leaves aside hundreds of academic journals that may comply with quality standards and are not indexed in curated collections -such as many that can be found in Open Edition (France) or Érudit (Canada). More examples can be found in Latin America (Salatino, 2017) or in Germany (Taubert, Sterzik & Bruns 2024): out of 509 diamond titles registered in the dataset, we found that 234 are not included in any kind of indexation system.

Hence, our aggregated dataset of indexed Diamond journals started with DOAJ, harvesting a total of 13.950 no-fee journals, which was compared with other 8 curated collections, using computational language R and crossing ISSN and title (See table included in Figure 2). The list of African Journals Online (AJOL) provided a total of 810 new titles. This was followed by the integration of JUFOS diamond journal list which contributed 161 journals. Latindex's list was the most numerous, adding 1,631 new titles, while SciELO's list provided 697 diamond journals. Redalyc's list added 270 journals and Biblat 18 new titles. Finally, we found 318 different diamond journals in Scopus and Web of Science.

Figure 2 and table 2

Cartography of no-fee indexed journals, n=17,855

Table 3 shows the distribution of the journals by country, Latin America being the region with the largest share with 29,2% of the total. Compared with the 25% attributed to this region in the Open Access Diamond Journal Study (2021), there is in fact an underrepresentation of the diamond journals published in this region. This share would surely enlarge if we add numerous non-indexed diamond journals. In the case of Europe, Spain (1,385) and Poland (726) provide the major number of indexed diamond journals and great part of the first is integrated in the Latindex Catalogue.

Table 3

Indexed Diamond Journals by country, n= 17,855

COUNTRY	N	COUNTRY	N	COUNTRY	N
Brazil	1,836	Austria	53	Tunisia	7
Spain	1,385	Ethiopia	52	Mongolia	7
Indonesia	1,340	Kenya	50	Iceland	7
Poland	726	Belgium	48	Libya	7
Argentina	638	Slovakia	46	Oman	6
United States	630	Bosnia & Herzegovina	45	Montenegro	6
Iran	592	Algeria	44	Angola	5

Colombia	579	Singapore	44	Brunei	5
Russia	560	Ghana	40	Congo - Kinshasa	5
Turkey	545	Tanzania	38	Senegal	4
Mexico	518	Paraguay	38	Israel	4
United Kingdom	508	Panama	37	Yemen	4
Italy	469	Bolivia	36	Eswatini	3
Ecuador	347	Morocco	35	Burkina Faso	3
Chile	331	Iraq	33	Kyrgyzstan	3
Romania	326	Moldova	33	Palestinian Territories	3
France	297	Japan	33	Mauritius	3
South Africa	297	Thailand	30	Malawi	3
Peru	280	Philippines	28	Côte d'Ivoire	3
Germany	279	Nepal	28	Botswana	3
India	265	Greece	27	Gambia	2
Nigeria	262	Guatemala	25	Malta	2
Ukraine	259	Sri Lanka	25	Congo - Brazzaville	2
Portugal	199	Nicaragua	24	Afghanistan	2
Finland	191	Estonia	23	Sudan	2
Serbia	190	Saudi Arabia	21	Jordan	2
Canada	180	Taiwan	20	Luxembourg	2
Cuba	175	Belarus	20	Zambia	2
Croatia	155	Ireland	20	South Sudan	2
Czechia	139	Uganda	20	Bhutan	1
Venezuela	123	New Zealand	20	Guadeloupe	1
Netherlands	117	El Salvador	16	Syria	1
Norway	114	Hong Kong SAR China	16	Bahrain	1
China	111	Puerto Rico	16	Uzbekistan	1
Costa Rica	110	Bangladesh	16	Togo	1
South Korea	103	Dominican Republic	16	Kuwait	1
Switzerland	98	Qatar	15	Trinidad & Tobago	1
Pakistan	93	North Macedonia	14	Burundi	1
Hungary	92	Vietnam	14	Eritrea	1
Egypt	88	Zimbabwe	13	Azerbaijan	1
Australia	84	Honduras	11	Lesotho	1
Slovenia	81	Cameroon	11	Benin	1
Malaysia	80	Armenia	11	Turkmenistan	1
Lithuania	79	Kazakhstan	10	Tajikistan	1
Internacionales	67	Latvia	10	Sierra Leone	1
Uruguay	64	Georgia	9	Barbados	1
Bulgaria	59	Rwanda	9	Mali	1
Denmark	53	Albania	8	Lebanon	1
Sweden	53	United Arab Emirates	8	Unidentifiable country	301
GRAND TOTAL					17,855

One of the main problems to determine the “diamond” feature of a journal resides in the lack of transparency of APC costs as discussed above, particularly in the commercial databases. Given the type of curated lists used as source for this research this issue had a minimal incidence, detected crossing our aggregated list with the dataset of APC by Butler et al. After this procedure 276 titles were spotted and detracted from our dataset. Table 4 shows the distribution by collection of this group of journals, 71 (25,7%) being published in the UK.

Table 4

Journals excluded, by platform n=276

PLATAFORMA	Q	%
DOAJ	196	71,00%
AJOL	2	0,70%
JUFO	3	1,10%
LATINDEX	22	8,00%
SCIELO	32	11,60%
WOS-SCOPUS	21	7,60%
TOTAL	276	100,00%

Another limitation in the data for the cartography was found in titles without information on the country, also with small incidence: 301 titles (See table 1). This could suggest that most of the diamond journals have an institutional anchorage in which case the geographical location is easily identifiable. Most of the titles with unidentifiable country are listed in WoS and Scopus.

Eventually, 5,209 of the total 17,855 diamond titles included in this cartography are published in Latin America. Different from Europe, where most journals have been created by learned societies, in Latin America most of these titles are published by universities (Beigel et al 2024). This may be a common feature of the diamond journals published in the global South (Debat et al 2025) considering, for example, the case of Indonesia (Widiantoa, Hadiyantoc & Mantorod 2025). But some countries in Europe, as in the case of Poland, have government support for scholarly journals edited in Universities all of which boosts this kind of venues (Kulczycki 2022).

Trzesniak (2009) stresses the advantages of the university journals related to credibility of the editors and scientific committees but also argues that it is critical to count on an adequate technical team to face the increasing edition flow. Some universities provide this institutional support, including access to digital infrastructure, administrative resources and staffing for editorial processes. Another relevant process that is frequently centralized or performed in a solidarian way is indexation. This can explain why most of the university journals are indexed in two or more collections with academic evaluation for entrance.

However, not all university journals are published with institutional support nor receive direct funding from university budgets. Nazarovets (2025) highlights that an institutional environment is one of the key factors for ensuring stability -and we could add also for ensuring diamond access- but the level and consistency of this support vary widely. This brings up one of the main questions of this research: how does this institutional diamond publishing work through the Latin American universities?

The University Portals in Latin America

One of the most extended publishing models for diamond journals in this region is the “university portal”, as a centralized space for the integration of editorial teams and/or as a mean for the dissemination of all the titles edited by the institution. A “University Portal” will be understood here as a website that compiles journals and integrates them into a single search interface. These portals not only exist on an institutional scale, but there are also portals that reunite titles on a national and regional scale. [Miguilim](#) is an outstanding national portal with metadata of 4,956 active Brazilian journals and 282 portals. Another national case is the [Portal de Revistas Académicas Chilenas](#), which contains information about 91 institutions and their 384 journals. A regional portal *par excellence* is [Latindex](#), with a directory of 28,612 titles and a Catalog collection with 4,056 journals subject to a rigorous evaluation for entrance.

In this section we will only address the University Portals managed at an institutional level of a given university located in Latin America, because they not only represent an information service for readers and authors, but also a kind of organization that tends to cooperatively fulfill editorial tasks and make a more efficient use of the human resources available. We found 741 university portals that represent 10,823 active journals. A great diversity was found in terms of the scope of the portals themselves, which can be described as a website providing basic visibility or as an organization aimed at offering hosting and editorial management services to the journals published by the university. Among these, they provide infrastructures such as persistent identifiers or digital preservation. When it is a form of organization, it can be a centralized editorial team working at the rectorates or directly by a department, at the library or the repository. These publishing offices normally are separated from the University Presses, frequently dedicated only to editing books.

The Portals are not always articulated with the library and/or the institutional Repositories. Argentina is an interesting case to observe this, considering that this country has a national Law establishing mandatory open access through the institutional Repositories. But many universities manage separately the journals coordinated by the portal and the general output normally published in the repository.

This results many times in duplications or invisibility of the journals at the local open infrastructures (Zo & Di Domenico 2025). A counterexample of good practices and interaction between the centralized Journal Portal and the Repository is [SEDICI](#) at Universidad Nacional de La Plata.

Table 5 shows that these university portals are distributed along the whole region, with the major shares in Brazil, Colombia, Argentina, Perú and México. However, México doesn't stand only for its share in the number of university portals but should be highlighted because it manages relevant regional Portals such as the already mentioned Latindex, along with established regional indexing systems such as Biblat and Redalyc. It is worth mentioning that both Mexico and Uruguay share a feature of a highly centralized structure of portals and journals given the great size of their historic universities (UNAM and UdelaR, respectively).

Table 5

Number of University portals per country, n=741

COUNTRY	NUMBER OF PORTALS	% PORTALS
BRAZIL	264	35,6%
COLOMBIA	98	13,2%
ARGENTINA	93	12,6%
PERÚ	59	8,0%
MÉXICO	52	7,0%
CHILE	40	5,4%
ECUADOR	35	4,7%
VENEZUELA	17	2,3%
BOLIVIA	14	1,9%
CUBA	12	1,6%
PARAGUAY	11	1,5%
URUGUAY	10	1,3%
COSTA RICA	10	1,3%
PANAMÁ	9	1,2%
EL SALVADOR	5	0,7%
GUATEMALA	5	0,7%
NICARAGUA	4	0,5%
HONDURAS	2	0,3%
PUERTO RICO	1	0,1%
GRAND TOTAL	741	100,0%

When analyzing the number of journals that these portals include per country (Table 6), we see that Brazil accounts for 52.8% (5,710) of the total 10,823 journals in the survey. In second place is Argentina, with 1,146 titles, Colombia with 993 and México accounting for 837 journals. The size of the public universities in these countries explain great part of the differences in terms of the share in the total portals.

Concerning now the difference between types of universities, more than half of the total portals (393) are managed by public institutions while 348 are run by private universities. Although 39.1% of these are in Brazil; 19.8% in Colombia (63); 9.8% in Peru (34). In the rest of the countries the dominant framework for the journals included in the portals is the public university as can be seen in Table 7.

Table 6

Number of journals by country, n=10,823

COUNTRY	N JOURNALS	% JOURNALS
BRAZIL	5,710	52,8
ARGENTINA	1,146	10,6
COLOMBIA	993	9,2
MEXICO	837	7,7
CHILE	447	4,1
PERU	439	4,1
VENEZUELA	322	3,0
ECUADOR	233	2,2
BOLIVIA	135	1,2
COSTA RICA	114	1,1
GUATEMALA	83	0,8
PANAMA	80	0,7
PARAGUAY	79	0,7
CUBA	55	0,5
URUGUAY	49	0,5
EL SALVADOR	32	0,3
NICARAGUA	27	0,2
PUERTO RICO	27	0,2
HONDURAS	15	0,1
GRAND TOTAL	10,823	100,0

Table 7

Number of journals by type of university, n=10,823

ROW LABELS	N JOURNALS	% JOURNALS
PUBLIC UNIVERSITY	6,613	62,9
PRIVATE UNIVERSITY	4,210	37,1
GRAND TOTAL	10,823	100.0

Our survey and the available literature on the Latin American publishing circuit shows that most of these journals are edited in OJS. The portals are also implemented very frequently in this same interface: 516 of the total 741. Among the rest we found more

frequent failures or even websites with errors. Among the portals that use OJS, 49.6% (256) correspond to private universities, while the remaining 50.4% (260) correspond to public universities. Out of the portals that use services other than OJS, 33.6% (44) correspond to private universities, while the remaining 66.4% (87) correspond to public universities. Finally, of the websites that failed to load, 51.1% (48) correspond to private universities, while the remaining 48.9% (46) correspond to public universities. Table 8 shows the relation between portals and number of journals in the mega-universities of Latin America that highlight in this kind of organization of publishing.

Table 8

Top 10 Universities by portal and number of journals included, n=46

UNIVERSITY	NUMBER OF PORTALS	NUMBER OF JOURNALS
UNIVERSIDAD DE BUENOS AIRES	5	236
UNIVERSIDADE DE SÃO PAULO (USP)	4	230
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL AUTÓNOMA DE MÉXICO	5	203
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE LA PLATA	7	110
UNIVERSIDAD DE CHILE	3	109
UNIVERSIDAD DE SAN CARLOS DE GUATEMALA	3	68
UNIVERSIDADE ESTADUAL PAULISTA "JÚLIO DE MESQUITA FILHO" (UNESP)	7	56
UNIVERSIDADE FEDERAL DE MINAS GERAIS (UFMG)	3	46
UNIVERSIDAD NACIONAL DE MAR DEL PLATA	4	42
UNIVERSIDAD DE LA REPÚBLICA	5	34
GRAND TOTAL	46	1,134

Only 131 portals provided enough information to verify the internal organization and the relation between visibility and management. In table 9 we can see that 48.1% of these portals are managed by centralized university administrations (63); 31.3% by faculties (41); 16.0% to publishing houses administrated by the Rectorate (21); and the remaining 4.6% correspond to other types of editorial managers (6).

Table 9

Editorial managers, n=131

RESPONSIBLE INSTITUTION	NUMBER OF EDITORIAL MANAGERS	% OF EDITORIAL MANAGERS
RECTOR'S OFFICE	63	48,1
FACULTY	41	31,3
EDITORIAL-RECTOR'S OFFICE	21	16,0
OTHERS	6	4,6
GRAND TOTAL	131	100,0

Conclusions

The recent importance of the communitarian feature of the journals confronts with the increasing marketization of scholarly publishing and brings up a debate about the definition of the feature and the scale of these “communities”. Given that a university journal is published by an institution, it is a pertinent question to ask whether these venues are led by disciplinary communities or should be considered as led by the scholarly community in a broad sense and eventually represented by the given university as an academic institution. An additional discussion comes along with the scale of this community, because many understand community-led journals as necessarily international, while others convey that an institutional journal may legitimately represent national inter-disciplinary fields or even locally relevant research fields.

Gatti, Mounier & Rooryck (2025) argue that most journals across both science and humanities disciplines are now owned and controlled by a very small number of large commercially orientated publishers because many learned societies now outsource the production, management, and revenue strategies of their journals. To regain academic autonomy, they argue, diamond publishing must be understood beyond institutional publishing. In this paper we argue that this ideal type of academic venue is based on the traditional European journal led by a Learned society, while the Latin American experience shows that the institutional anchorage could be the unique available shield to confront the current state of marketization.

Many reasons support this argument. First, University journals in Latin America are mainly featured by diamond open access, therefore, there is little incidence of the hybrid publishing model or the combination of several paywalls. Second, the wingspan acquired by the current publishing system does not allow much space for a nostalgic return to the artisan good old small (printed) journals of the 1990s. The manuscript flow and the complexity of rigorous peer review require professional editorial teams capable of solving technical tasks for the academic editors to fulfill

adequately their role. Third, university journals are developed in the same environment where institutional and national research assessment systems evolve. This is why these venues make sustained efforts tend to reach international or national indexation in curated collections to add value to the researchers and a stimulus to send their papers. The global cartography of diamond journals presented in this paper shows that 47,5% of the total 17,855 indexed diamond journals are included in two or more collections with academic evaluation for entrance.

Numerous initiatives and academic organizations have raised awareness on the marketization of publishing and the need to strengthen the future of scholarly communication towards diamondisation. In several reports and conferences Latin America appears as the model to follow in this direction. However, the features of the publishing landscape in this region are not yet fully acknowledged nor are the different editorial models which have not been deeply examined. Our survey suggests that this regional model of scholarly journals managed through university portals is highly diverse, although it can represent an efficient way towards sustainability and a strong path to retain/regain academic autonomy.

Data accessibility statement

The datasets corresponding to 7 cartographies for Inclusive Open Science can be consulted in: <https://ri.conicet.gov.ar/handle/11336/256625>

The datasets corresponding to this article will be uploaded soon.

Competing Interests

The authors have no competing interests to declare.

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